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Electroneurography vs. Neural Reality: Hidden Fallacies in Nerve Conduction Studies

Electromyography (EMG) studies the muscle's response to an electrical stimulus. Whether this stimulus is an external electrical current or an internal electrical current originating from the nerve supplying the muscle, the result is unequivocally the same. Therefore, EMG in particular will remain outside the scope of this discussion.

Conversely, Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) will be the focal point and the core of my upcoming critical study, for it is where the illusory battles the real.

The Illusory and the Real

The researcher places an electrode on the skin surface directly over the nerve under investigation. They deliver an artificial electrical impulse through it. Subsequently, they receive this electrical impulse at a distal point further along the same nerve pathway. As a result, the researcher obtains a graphical trace and values, including the Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV).

The researcher assumed that the artificial electrical current would propagate along the same pathway as the organic neural transmission current. He believed both traveled along the surface of the axon. Consequently, he reasoned, the result for measuring nerve conduction velocity would be the same, since it's electricity in both cases, and the propagation pathway is identical in both scenarios.

The researcher employs this concept in approaching nerve injuries, yielding correct results at times, but ambiguous ones in many other instances. The correct results reinforced his concept of the traditional mechanism of neural transmission, until it became deeply rooted, not only in his own perception but also in the collective perception of his followers. As for the erroneous results, he unjustly attributed them to the inadequacy of the techniques in detecting these processes. As for his

conceptions about neural transmission, they were the immutable truth, utterly unassailable under any circumstances... That is how it was.

Revolution of Concepts

*In an article of mine titled "[Neural Transmission: Between a Deficient Heritage and a Present New Paradigm](#)," I extensively elaborated on my novel perspective of the neural transmission mechanism within axons. Space here does not permit a full exposition of the idea, but succinctly stated: In true neural transmission, **action electrical currents** are carried upon an **action pressure wave**. Both the electrical currents and the pressure wave propagate inside the axon within its **lumen**, not along the surface of its **myelin sheath**.*

Therefore, the artificial electrical current will not match the true action electrical currents involved in actual neural signal transmission—except in directionality and perhaps in its effect on the effector organ.

*Their propagation pathways, however, differ fundamentally. While the path of the former (artificial current) is **parietal/superficial** (along the wall), the path of the latter (true neural transmission) is **deep within the axon's lumen**.*

Fortuitous Coincidence!

*One might argue: In **myelin sheath injuries**, neural transmission consistently slows down. Doesn't this suggest some role for the axonal wall in the neural transmission process? That is the first point. Secondly, in these same myelin injuries, traditional measurement tools—the very **electromyograph (EMG)** under indictment—can still detect a significant decrease in conduction velocities.*

The perplexing question here is: How can a technique you claim is fundamentally flawed yield correct results that align with the actual pathological state of the organism?

*I respond: Yes... in your example, what you describe does occur. But this is merely an **auspicious coincidence**, nothing more. The results of the traditional nerve study coincided with the organism's true condition because, in this specific context, **the***

*illusory converged with the real. Both the **external artificial current** and the **true neural transmission current** share a dependency on the importance of the **myelin sheath** for neural transmission within the nerve fiber.*

The myelin sheath is the exclusive conduit for the external electrical current used in electrodiagnostic studies. When it is damaged, the propagation of this artificial current is inevitably impaired and delayed in reaching the recording electrode.

*As for the **true neural transmission currents**, their relationship with the **myelin sheath** is profoundly different—even if it appears otherwise. To understand this relationship, a closely related preamble is essential.*

(Between Parentheses)

*The velocity of **true neural transmission** fundamentally depends on the speed of the **action pressure wave** within it. The speed of this wave—which, incidentally, is a **longitudinal wave**—is determined by the diameter of the axon. As this diameter increases, the **wavelength** of the action pressure waves propagating inside it lengthens, and consequently, their **wave velocity** increases.*

*Discussing rapidly propagating action pressure waves is equivalent to discussing high-energy **action waves** with both kinetic and potential components. Similarly, it implies elevated **pressure values** inside the axon—both at **resting pressure** and during **action pressure**.*

*The **cell membrane** of the nerve fiber cannot independently withstand high resting pressure values, let alone the significantly higher pressures of action waves. Here, the **myelin sheath** intervenes to enhance the membrane's resistance and increase its capacity to endure high-energy, high-velocity action pressure waves. This endurance is foundational for **high-efficiency, high-speed neural transmission**.*

*Thus, in **myelin sheath injuries**, the organism becomes unable to:*

- 1. Sustain high-value resting pressure,*
- 2. Generate high-velocity, high-energy action pressure waves.*

*The inevitable and factual result is **decreased neural conduction velocity**.*

Return to the Beginning

The two concepts—the old, illusory one and my new, true one—converge on the importance of the myelin sheath in achieving high neural conduction velocities, even if they differ in their operational mechanisms. In both, the propagation speed of electrical current decreases with myelin sheath injury.

What traditional diagnostic tools like the electromyograph (EMG) detect is specifically the reduced propagation speed of the artificially applied electrical current forced upon the organism. Meanwhile, the true decrease in speed of the operational neural transmission currents remains entirely beyond the reach of these aforementioned instruments.

Yet, fortunately, the two emergent alterations happened to align in the same direction: Here, a decrease in the speed of the artificial electrical current; there, a decrease in the speed of the operational electrical currents during true neural transmission. Thus, the former (artificial measurement) indirectly signaled the latter (biological reality), without necessarily being it.

Truth is an Indivisible Whole

If your concept is correct, how do you explain numerous pathological cases where neural function is entirely absent, yet the conduction velocity recorded by your criticized instruments remains normal or nearly so?

In degenerative axonal lesions, normal motor response in the effector muscle is lost, while traditional measurement devices continue to register normal conduction velocities. Let us examine this phenomenon through both perspectives on neural transmission: the prevailing illusory one and my true model.

In the illusory model:

Neural transmission persists (as measured) due to an intact myelin sheath conducting the artificial current. Functional action is absent because of the loss of axonal substance.

In the true model:

The reality is precisely the opposite. In axonal degeneration:

1. ***True conduction velocity decreases*** alongside functional efficacy.
2. ***Conduction fails*** due to loss of structural axonal material—specifically ***vesicles*** in the axon lumen.
3. ***Function is lost*** due to the absence of vesicles and their cargo of neural transmission mediators from:
 - *The presynaptic terminal (**knob**),*
 - *And the **synaptic cleft**.*

Axonal substance is the essential medium (mount) for both the ***action pressure wave*** and its resulting ***operational transmission currents***. For pressure waves cannot propagate through emptiness.

As for ***microscopic vesicles*** and their cargo—the ***neurotransmitter***—they are the ultimate purpose of neural transmission: its ***final messengers*** to the target organ across the ***synaptic cleft***.

Functional action cannot exist without neurotransmitters filling the synaptic cleft. Yet neurotransmitters themselves hold no significance unless the action pressure wave first reaches the neural synapse.

Crucial Note: *Rigorous analysis and exhaustive detail of these mechanisms can be found in my articles:*

1. [*Neural Transmission: Between an Inadequate Heritage and a Contemporary New Paradigm*](#)
2. [*Transmission at the Neural Synapse: A Mechanistic Revision*](#)
3. [*Wallerian Degeneration: A Novel Perspective*](#)

Therefore, neural conduction velocity decreases in degenerative axonal lesions due to:

1. **Rarefaction of the intra-axonal medium**, which negatively impacts the propagation speed of action pressure waves.
2. **Absent effector function** from missing neurotransmitters in the synaptic cleft.

Yet traditional diagnostic instruments (EMG/NCV) fail to detect or record this impairment because they are founded on an invalid conceptual premise.

Parenthetical Statement

To understand the **functional action** of neural transmission, one must recall the role of:

1. The **neurotransmitter**
2. The **microscopic vesicles** carrying it.

Neurotransmitters are synthesized in the **neuron soma**, stored within vesicles, and transported along the axon to the **terminal synapse**—where they become essential for relaying neural signals to the **effector organ**. I will not delve into granular details here, as even this domain lacks consensus between established and personal perspectives.

Upon reaching the synapse, neural transmission requires neurotransmitters to cross the **synaptic cleft** and activate the effector organ (e.g., another neuron, muscle, etc.). **Absence of neurotransmitter** severs functional connectivity at the synaptic cleft, halting neural transmission. Thus, **no functional action occurs without neurotransmitter saturation of the synaptic cleft.**

Unfortunate Luck

Here, the results of traditional nerve studies **diverged from the organism's true condition**. Your instrument failed to detect the actual pathological variables because the illusory does not match reality—even when it mimics it. **The true pathological changes** in axonal degeneration lie in one realm; **What your device records** lies in another. **This time, fortune did not intervene**—revealing with stark clarity the flaws in your conceptual model of neural transmission.

The List Grows Longer

*This is but a **drop in the ocean**—a fraction of the evidence. The catalog of limitations in electrodiagnostic nerve studies grows ever longer. I will mention one case that long puzzled me—not as **proof**, but as **dark illustration**—leaving its full analysis for future research.*

*Consider a patient presenting with **unequivocal neurological symptoms**:*

- *Clear clinical signs of **nerve compression***
- *Pain and sensory disturbances in the nerve's territory*
- *A positive **Tinel's sign** (tingling on nerve percussion)*

*All attest to the nerve's distress. Yet the electrodiagnostic report shows **absolutely no neural pathology**. How? Why?*

Essence of the Matter

*The **illusory model** (traditional electrodiagnostics) and the **true model** (my hydrodynamic framework) converge only on **myelin's structural necessity** for neural conduction velocity. This coincidence allows their readings to align in myelinopathies. Beyond this narrow context, they diverge fundamentally—revealing traditional methods' profound inadequacy.*

How could it be otherwise? The foundation is illusory and flawed. What is built upon error is false—false, false, false—until breath itself ceases.

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In other contexts, one can also read the following articles:

[DOI *The Spinal Reflex, New Hypothesis of Physiology*](#)

- [*The Hyperreflexia, Innovated Pathophysiology*](#)

[DOI *The Spinal Shock*](#)

- - [*The Spinal Injury, the Pathophysiology of the Spinal Shock, the Pathophysiology of the Hyperreflexia*](#)
- DOI [*Upper Motor Neuron Lesions, the Pathophysiology of the Symptomatology*](#)
- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(1\), the Pathophysiology of Hyperactivity*](#)
- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(2\), the Pathophysiology of Bilateral Responses*](#)
- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(3\), the Pathophysiology of Extended Hyperreflex*](#)
- - [*The Hyperreflexia \(4\), the Pathophysiology of Multi-Response Hyperreflex*](#)
- [*The pathophysiology of Triple flexion Reflex*](#)
- - [*The Clonus, 1st Hypothesis of Pathophysiology*](#)
- - [*The Clonus, 2nd Hypothesis of Pathophysiology*](#)
- DOI [*The Clonus, Two Hypotheses of Pathophysiology*](#)

- DOI [*The Nerve Transmission through Neural Fiber, Personal View vs. International View*](#)
- - [*The Nerve Transmission through Neural Fiber \(1\), The Action Pressure Waves*](#)
- - [*The Nerve Transmission through Neural Fiber \(2\), The Action Potentials*](#)
- - [*The Nerve Transmission through Neural Fiber \(3\), The Action Electrical Currents*](#)
- - [*The Function of Standard Action Potentials & Currents*](#)
- - [*The Three Phases of Nerve transmission*](#)

- DOI [*Neural Conduction in the Synapse \(Innovated\)*](#)

- DOI *Nodes of Ranvier, the Equalizers*
- - *Nodes of Ranvier, the Functions*
- - *Nodes of Ranvier, First Function*
- - *Nodes of Ranvier, Second Function*
- - *Nodes of Ranvier, Third Function*
- - *Node of Ranvier, The Anatomy*

- - *The Wallerian Degeneration*
- - *The Neural Regeneration*
- - *The Wallerian Degeneration Attacks Motor Axons, While Avoids Sensory Axons*

- DOI *The Sensory Receptors*

- - *Nerve Conduction Study, Wrong Hypothesis is the Origin of the Misinterpretation (Innovated)*

- DOI *Piriformis Muscle Injection: Personal Approach*

- - *The Philosophy of Pain, Pain Comes First! (Innovated)*
- - *The Philosophy of the Form (Innovated)*
- - *Pronator Teres Syndrome, Struthers-Like Ligament (Innovated)*
- - *Ulnar Nerve, Congenital Bilateral Dislocation*

- - [Posterior Interosseous Nerve Syndrome](#)
- - [The Multiple Sclerosis: The Causative Relationship Between The Galvanic Current & Multiple Sclerosis?](#)
- - [Cauda Equina Injury, New Surgical Approach](#)
- DOI [Carpal Tunnel Syndrome Ends Its Adherence: Complete Median Nerve Transection](#)
- DOI [Biceps Femoris' Long Head Syndrome \(BFLHS\)](#)

- DOI [Barr Body, The Whole Story \(Innovated\)](#)
- - [Adam's Rib and Adam's Apple, Two Faces of one Sin](#)
- - [Adam's Rib, could be the Original Sin?](#)
- - [Barr Body, the Second Look](#)

- DOI [Who Decides the Sex of Coming Baby?](#)
- - [Boy or Girl, Mother Decides!](#)
- - [Oocytogenesis](#)
- - [Spermatogenesis](#)
- - [This Woman Can Only Give Birth to Female Children](#)
- - [This Woman Can Only Give Birth to Male Children](#)
- - [This Woman Can Give Birth to Female Children More Than to Male Children](#)
- - [This Woman Can Give Birth to Male Children More Than to Female Children](#)
- - [This Woman Can Equally Give Birth to Male Children & to Female Children](#)

 - [*Eye Saved Human Identity; Adam Ensured Human Adaptation*](#)

 [DOI *COVID-19: Beyond the Crisis—Is It Targeting Our Genes?*](#)

[DOI *Fibromyalgia*](#)

 - [*Mitosis in Animal Cell*](#)

 - [*Meiosis*](#)

 - [*Universe Creation, Hypothesis of Continuous Cosmic Nebula*](#)

 - [*Circulating Sweepers*](#)

 - [*The Black Hole is a \(the\) Falling Star?*](#)

 - [*Pneumatic Petrous, Bilateral Temporal Hyperpneumatization*](#)

 [DOI *Congenital Bilateral Thenar Hypoplasia*](#)

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